

Exploring Re3data.org - Your Gateway to Open Access Research Data

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the role of Re3data.org in research and conducts a detailed analysis of global research data repositories listed in the database. Divided into two main sections, it examines various aspects such as subject categories, content types, country involvement, institution classifications, language preferences, software usage, metadata standards, quality management, data access, and prevalent keywords. The aim is to provide comprehensive insights and guidance for researchers and institutions, facilitating better data sharing, access, and repository management practices. Ultimately, this research seeks to optimize research methodologies and enhance accessibility to valuable research data worldwide.

Keywords: Research Data Repositories, Re3data.org, Data Management, Open Access, Data Analysis

Introduction

In today's research landscape, open access to data stands as a catalyst for innovation and collaboration. It redefines how knowledge is shared, fostering transparency and accelerating discoveries across disciplines. The unrestricted availability of research data fuels scientific inquiry and promotes reproducibility, driving breakthroughs that address global challenges. The demand for proficient data management became more pronounced following the introduction of the widely acknowledged FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Researchers, academic institutions, and funding entities began addressing this concern through policies, programs, collaborative efforts, and infrastructural developments (Pampel & Bertelmann, 2011). For instance, the National Science Foundation (NSF) in the United States implemented a Data Sharing Policy in 2011, mandating grant recipients to furnish details about data management through a Data Management Plan (National Science Board, 2011). Similarly, in Germany, the German Research Foundation (DFG) issued a comparable directive on research data accessibility during the 2010s (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, n.d.) (Wissenschaftsorganisationen, 2010).

Embracing this paradigm shift, Re3data.org emerges as a crucial platform. It serves as a centralized registry of research data repositories, offering researchers worldwide easy access to a vast array of openly available datasets. Re3data.org's significance lies in its role as a repository aggregator, simplifying the daunting task of discovering and accessing diverse datasets. By providing a user-friendly interface, it facilitates collaboration, innovation, and knowledge exchange among researchers, shaping the landscape of open access to research data.

The study is structured into two main sections: the initial part delves into the pivotal role played by Re3data.org in research. The subsequent section involves a comprehensive analysis of the research data repository landscape listed in Re3data.org. Through the utilization of various search filters, this research extensively explores subject categorizations, content types, country involvement, institution and repository classifications, language preferences, software usage, metadata standards, quality management, data access, and prevalent keywords across globally registered repositories. The overarching aim is to provide a holistic understanding of these repositories, offering valuable insights to optimize data sharing, access methods, and repository management practices for both researchers and institutions.

Re3data.org: A Comprehensive Overview

Re3data.org is a global registry of research data repositories established in 2012 and funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) and involves partners such as the Berlin School of Library and Information Science at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, the Helmholtz Open Science Office at GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, the KIT Library at Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), and the Libraries of Purdue University. It serves as a comprehensive resource, encompassing repositories across various academic disciplines, facilitating permanent storage and access to datasets for researchers, funding bodies, and publishers.

Re3data promotes a culture of sharing and increased data access while being referenced in editorial policies by publishers and journals like Copernicus Publications, PeerJ, Springer, and Nature's Scientific Data. Moreover, it's recommended in the European Commission's "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020." It merged with Databib under DataCite in 2015, aiming to consolidate services and eliminate redundancy.

Recently, starting in January 2020, the DFG has been funding the project "re3data - Community Driven Open Reference for Research Data Repositories (COREF)" focusing on enhancing repository descriptions, machine-to-machine communication, and becoming a trusted resource for the scientific community through the development of an advanced API and user-friendly tools (Re3data.org, n.d.-a).

Submission Process: Adding a Repository to Re3data.org

To add a research data repository (RDR) to re3data, complete an application form with essential details such as the repository's name, URL, and key properties. The project team meticulously evaluates the submission, using a handbook to assess the RDR's website for metadata properties aligned with the re3data schema. Meeting the minimum requirements outlined in the re3data policy is crucial, ensuring clarity in data and repository access, well-defined terms of use, and a primary focus on research data (Re3data.org, n.d.-b). A thorough review by a second team member validates the information before the RDR entry is published, making it visible within the re3data registry (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Workflow of Re3data Repository Submission Process

Source: Re3data.org (n.d.-b)

Literature Review

The literature review encompassed various studies examining research data repositories (RDRs) listed in re3data.org. **Kim (2018)** scrutinized contributions and organizational types of leading Asian economies within the repository, revealing disparities in country involvement and subject contributions. **Bhardwaj (2019)** traced Indian RDR development, highlighting content coverage and metadata standards, notably focusing on Life Sciences. **Gurikar and Hadagali (2020)** explored open data repositories indexed in re3data, identifying a strong presence of Science and Technology data from European and North American contributors. **Arora and Chakravarty (2021)** emphasized structured data in developed countries and scientific/statistical data prevalence in life sciences within RDM activities on re3data. **Gohain (2021)**

evaluated re3data's repository services, revealing contributions from various countries and organization types. **Kim (2021)** analyzed metadata formats and data version control in ecological field research repositories, stressing data quality improvements. Prashar and Chander (2022) delved into Computer Science repositories' characteristics in re3data, emphasizing repository features and access policies. **Archana S.N. and Padmakumar P.K. (2023)** explored Indian RDRs, highlighting disciplinary orientations and urging improvements in repository completeness. **Khan et al. (2023)** unveiled global RDR trends from re3data, emphasizing software usage, metadata standards, and open access characteristics across diverse repositories. Lastly, **Subaveerapandiyam A (2023)** provided a comprehensive review of RDM practices and challenges faced by academic libraries worldwide, stressing the role of libraries in supporting open science and data sharing. These studies collectively portrayed a diverse landscape, content coverage, and challenges within RDRs, offering insights for policymakers, researchers, and repository developers to enhance data access, quality, and repository management.

1. Study Objectives

The primary objectives of this study are to:

- Describe the role of Re3data.org in research
- Ascertain subject categorization within Re3data.org.
- Identify the diverse content types available in Re3data.org.
- Determine the country demonstrating the highest engagement in sharing research data on Re3data.org.
- Examine the various institution types associated with the indexed repositories.
- Analyze the repository classifications present in Re3data.org.
- Identify the prevalent language used within repositories on Re3data.org.
- Evaluate the software types predominantly utilized in Re3data.org repositories.
- Assess the most favored metadata standards employed by repositories within Re3data.org.
- Scrutinize the quality management mechanisms implemented in Re3data.org repositories.
- Investigate the data access status across repositories featured in Re3data.org.
- Identify the frequently used keywords within repositories listed on Re3data.org.

2. Section A: The Role of Re3data.org in Research

2.1. Facilitating Discovery and Access to Research Data

Re3data.org stands as a critical facilitator, offering an extensive registry that simplifies the discovery and accessibility of research data. Through its user-friendly interface and robust search functionalities, the platform empowers researchers to easily explore and access diverse datasets (Pampel et al., 2013). By providing comprehensive repository information, including subject coverage, content types, and metadata standards, it streamlines the search process, fostering transparency and accessibility in the research data landscape (Ye et al., 2023).

2.2. Supporting Reproducibility and Transparency in Research

The platform plays a vital role in supporting research reproducibility and transparency. It provides detailed metadata, enabling the replication and validation of research outcomes (Medina et al., 2022). By promoting transparency through data categorization, management standards, and access protocols, Re3data.org empowers researchers to validate findings, enhancing the credibility and integrity of research endeavors (Makani, 2015).

2.3. Enhancing Collaboration and Interdisciplinary Studies

Re3data.org encourages collaboration among researchers from diverse disciplines. Serving as a platform for accessing varied datasets, it fosters cross-disciplinary research and exploration. The platform facilitates collaborative efforts, nurturing innovation and knowledge creation across different domains, thus promoting interdisciplinary studies (Aguilar & Bernal, 2023).

2.4. Impact on Academic and Scientific Communities

Re3data.org significantly influences academic and scientific communities by acting as a valuable resource hub for research data. It enhances data visibility, accessibility, and credibility within scholarly

circles. Providing increased opportunities for collaboration, data discovery, and informed decision-making within institutions, it contributes to the advancement and integrity of academic and scientific pursuits (Redkina, 2021).

3. Section B: Exploring the Re3data.org Database

3.1. Research Methodology

The research methodology involves collecting data from Re3data.org's websites (<https://www.re3data.org>). To fulfill the study's objectives, 11 distinct search filters were employed. These approaches encompass subject, content, country, institution type, repository classification, language, software utilization, metadata standards, quality management practices, data access, and keywords. Data collection took place on December 31, 2023, capturing a sample (N) of 5340 registered data repositories. Subsequently, the gathered data underwent analysis and visualization using MS Excel to enhance comprehension across the aforementioned 11 parameters.

3.2. Data Analysis and Discussion

3.2.1. Subject Categories

By the end of December 31, 2023, Re3data platform hosted a total of 5340 registered research data repositories, broadly classified across four primary disciplines: Humanities & Social Sciences, Life Sciences, Natural Sciences, and Engineering Sciences. Notably, Life Sciences represented the highest share of repositories at 33.97%, followed closely by Natural Sciences at 30.58%, with Humanities and Social Sciences comprising 22.42%, and Engineering Sciences at 13.03%. Upon closer examination within specific subject disciplines within the Re3data platform, Basic Biological and Medical Research held the largest repository count (570), followed by Medicine (448), Physics (343), Social Sciences (315), Zoology (283), and Chemistry (261). This observation suggests a more structured approach to Research Data Management (RDM) within Life Sciences, Natural Sciences and Social Sciences compared to Humanities and Engineering Sciences.

Figure 2: Subject Categories of the Repositories in Re3data.org

3.2.2. Content Types

Table 2 showcases the categorization of content within all registered databases on the Re3data platform across 14 primary categories. Notably, Scientific and statistical data formats lead with a coverage of 37.58%, closely followed by Standard office documents at 37.04%. Additionally, Images, Raw data, and Plain text exhibit coverages of 29.55%, 25.30%, and 23.28%, respectively. Besides these 14 broad categories, there are also 1118 repositories that contain other content types. These classifications offer valuable insights into how researchers, scientists, social scientists, and engineers manage research data across diverse content categories.

Table 2: Content Types of the Repositories in Re3data.org

Rank	Content types	Repositories	Percentage (N=5340)
1	Scientific and statistical data formats	2007	37.58%
2	Standard office documents	1978	37.04%
3	Images	1578	29.55%
4	Raw data	1351	25.30%
5	Plain text	1243	23.28%
6	Structured graphics	1055	19.76%
7	Structured text	1036	19.40%
8	Archived data	765	14.33%
9	Databases	676	12.66%
10	Audiovisual data	633	11.85%
11	Software applications	495	9.27%
12	Source code	274	5.13%
13	Networkbased data	164	3.07%
14	Configuration data	98	1.84%

3.2.3. Countries of the Repositories

As of today, 88 countries actively participate in exchanging their research data through registered repositories on the Re3data platform. Table 3 highlights the top 15 countries and their respective contribution coverage to the platform. The United States leads with a coverage of 22.04%, hosting 1177 repositories, securing the top position. Following closely are Germany, Canada, and the United Kingdom, with coverages of 9.46%, 7.42%, and 6.07%, respectively, ranking second, third, and fourth. India, with a coverage of 0.96%, holds the 14th position among all countries listed. This distribution not only reflects the generation of research data but also underscores the level of openness and transparency within each country's research practices.

Table 3: Countries of the Repositories in Re3data.org

Rank	Country	Repositories	Percentage (N=5340)
1	United States	1177	22.04%
2	Germany	505	9.46%
3	Canada	396	7.42%
4	United Kingdom	324	6.07%
5	European Union	289	5.41%
6	International	282	5.28%
7	France	130	2.43%
8	Australia	103	1.93%
9	Switzerland	84	1.57%
10	China	81	1.52%
11	Netherlands	78	1.46%
12	Japan	66	1.24%
13	Spain	55	1.03%
14	India	51	0.96%
15	Italy	50	0.94%

3.2.4. Institution Types

Research, mainly scientific, medical and engineering research involved several funding, sponsoring, commercialization and technical aspects. This section provides insights of the institution types from where the research data of the repository comes from.

Figure 3: Institution Type of the Repositories in Re3data.org

Figure 3 illustrates the composition of the 5340 registered repositories in the Re3data platform. It shows that 3127 (58.56%) repositories are non-profit entities, while 158 (2.96%) are associated with commercial institutions. Additionally, there are 2055 repositories where the institution type is unspecified or not mentioned within the Re3data platform.

3.2.5. Repository Types

The Re3data platform categorizes repositories into three main types: Disciplinary, Institutional, and Other. Disciplinary repositories curate research data specifically linked to particular subjects or disciplines. Institutional repositories, also referred to as the green route of repository, manage research data associated with a particular institution. Other repository types encompass organized data that does not fall under the categories of disciplinary or institutional repositories.

Figure 4: Repository Types in Re3data.org

Within the repositories indexed on the Re3data platform, 44.06% (2353) are categorized as disciplinary, while 16.69% (891) are institutional in nature. Additionally, 6.97% (372) fall under the category of other repositories. Notably, 32.28% (1724) of repositories remain unspecified or unknown (Figure 4).

3.2.6. Languages of the Repositories

The Re3data platform encompasses data in a total of 61 languages from diverse regions worldwide, with many repositories containing data in multiple languages. Table 4 delineates the top 15 languages represented in the data repositories on the Re3data platform. Notably, over half of the repositories are in English (57.30%). Beyond English, German (5.32%), French (5.13%), Spanish (2.75%), and Chinese (1.67%) databases constitute more than 1% coverage each. Among Indian languages, only "Hindi" comprises a significant portion, with six repositories in its coverage.

Table 4: Languages of the Repositories in Re3data.org

Rank	Language	Repositories	Percentage (N=5340)
1	English	3060	57.30%
2	German	284	5.32%
3	French	274	5.13%
4	Spanish; Castilian	147	2.75%
5	Chinese	89	1.67%
6	Portuguese	50	0.94%
7	Japanese	48	0.90%
8	Dutch	43	0.81%
9	Russian	41	0.77%
10	Italian	33	0.62%
11	Polish	32	0.60%
12	Swedish	23	0.43%
13	Finnish	17	0.32%
14	Catalan; Valencian	16	0.30%
14	Danish	16	0.30%
15	Czech	14	0.26%

3.2.7. Software Types

The data repositories indexed within the Re3data platform utilize various types of software for the creation and maintenance of research data. Table 5 illustrates 11 prominent software solutions commonly employed in these repositories. Notably, Dataverse (3.35%) and DSpace (2.49%) hold the top two positions. Additionally, CKAN (1.85%) and MySQL (1.69%) also represent notable software choices. However, it's important to highlight that the software used in approximately 22.24% (1188) of repositories remains unidentified or unmentioned within the Re3data platform.

Table 5: Software Types of the Repositories in Re3data.org

Rank	Software Types	Repositories	Percentage (N=5340)
1	Dataverse	179	3.35%
2	DSpace	133	2.49%
3	CKAN	99	1.85%
4	MySQL	90	1.69%
5	Fedora	48	0.90%
6	EPrints	35	0.66%
7	Nesstar	17	0.32%
8	DigitalCommons	5	0.09%
8	eSciDoc	5	0.09%
9	dLibra	4	0.07%
10	Opus	3	0.06%

3.2.8. Used Metadata Standards

The metadata employed to describe web resources are crucial for organizing, accessing, and exchanging data within online repositories. A dependable research data repository typically adheres to or supports multiple metadata standards. The Re3data platform, for instance, upholds 28 such standards, with the top 15 outlined in Table 6. Notably, Dublin Core stands out as the most utilized metadata standard, boasting a coverage of 10.51%, closely followed by the DataCite Metadata Schema at 7.23%. Additionally, DDI - Data Documentation Initiative, Repository-Developed Metadata Schemas, and ISO 19115 are noteworthy, accounting for coverages of 5.11%, 4.10%, and 3.80%, respectively.

Table 6: Used Metadata Standards of the Repositories in Re3data.org

Rank	Metadata Standard	Repositories	Percentage (N=5340)
1	Dublin Core	561	10.51%
2	DataCite Metadata Schema	386	7.23%
3	DDI - Data Documentation Initiative	273	5.11%
4	Repository-Developed Metadata Schemas	219	4.10%
5	ISO 19115	203	3.80%
6	FGDC/CSDGM - Federal Geographic Data Committee Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata	102	1.91%
7	OAI-ORE - Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange	94	1.76%
8	CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions	46	0.86%
9	DIF - Directory Interchange Format	44	0.82%
10	Darwin Core	40	0.75%
11	EML - Ecological Metadata Language	38	0.71%
12	DCAT - Data Catalog Vocabulary	32	0.60%
13	RDF Data Cube Vocabulary	25	0.47%
14	ABCD - Access to Biological Collection Data	19	0.36%
14	ISA-Tab	19	0.36%
15	International Virtual Observatory Alliance Technical Specifications	13	0.24%

3.2.9. Quality Management

Repositories that promote or do not support quality control are included in the quality management program division. Within the Re3data platform, all licensed study data archives are grouped into three quality monitoring systems, i.e. Yes, No and Unknown.

Figure 5: Quality Management of the Repositories in Re3data.org

According to Figure 5, among the 5340 indexed repositories, 32.95% (1706) provide information regarding quality control measures, while a small percentage, 0.99% (53) of repositories lack any reported quality management system. Notably, information regarding the quality control practices for the remaining 67.06% (3581) repositories is uncertain or unknown.

3.2.10. Access Status

The accessibility of research data is a pivotal aspect for repositories. As depicted in Figure 6, the current status of data accessibility among the indexed repositories in the Re3data platform varies. Approximately 51.25% (2737) of repositories are openly accessible to all users. Following this, 28.86% (1541) have restricted access, 9.14% (488) impose an embargo on access, and 5.04% (269) maintain closed data access. Notably, the access status of the remaining 5.71% (305) repositories is either unknown or unmentioned within the Re3data platform.

Figure 6: Data Access Status of the Repositories in Re3data.org

3.2.11. Used Keywords

In addition to browsing repositories by subject, users can also navigate repositories by keywords. Hence, including adequate and pertinent keywords for each repository is crucial for identification and easy access to its contents. Within the Re3data platform, all registered research data repositories are categorized into 30 keyword classifications. Table 7 presents the top 15 categories among them. Analysis reveals that 404 repositories (7.57%) encompass data related to multidisciplinary subjects, followed by FAIR, genomics, health, bioinformatics, and genetics in the ranking.

Table 7: Keywords Used in Repositories of Re3data.org

Rank	Keywords	Frequency	Percentage
1	multidisciplinary	404	7.57
2	FAIR	236	4.42
3	genomics	144	2.70
4	health	127	2.38
5	bioinformatics	120	2.25
6	genetics	113	2.12
7	biodiversity	106	1.99
8	biology	96	1.80
9	climate	86	1.61
10	DNA	83	1.55
11	agriculture	82	1.54
12	meteorology	80	1.50
13	environment	77	1.44
14	atmosphere	75	1.40
15	COVID-19	74	1.39

Discussion and Conclusion

The study's comprehensive analysis of Re3data.org underscores the platform's critical role in cataloging research data repositories globally. Despite over a decade since its inception, the platform continues to face challenges in achieving widespread participation, particularly from developing nations. This limitation impedes the platform's intended purpose of fostering open access to research data, exacerbated by repository owners' preference for restrictive access measures. Moreover, the prevalence of English-language repositories indicates a lack of linguistic diversity, further restricting accessibility.

Nevertheless, Re3data.org serves as an invaluable initial step towards global data sharing and remains a cornerstone resource for the research community. Its significance lies in its potential to evolve into a more inclusive and diverse platform, encouraging greater involvement from a broader spectrum of countries, organizations, and scientific communities. Embracing a more open-access culture and language diversity could enhance the platform's efficacy in facilitating global knowledge exchange.

The study's findings emphasize the need for concerted efforts to encourage broader participation, ensure open access to research data, and diversify languages represented within Re3data.org. Such

enhancements are pivotal for maximizing the platform's utility, enabling widespread knowledge dissemination, and advancing global research collaboration in the future.

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